

Cation Exchange Separation of Iron, Cobalt and Nickel by Combined Ion Exchange Solvent Extraction Technique

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In the present paper, a method is described for the selective separation of iron, cobalt and nickel. The technique is based on the uptake of the metal ions on Amberlite IR-120, a strong acid cation exchange resin and then eluting with acetone-hydrochloric acid mixtures. The method can be successfully employed to separate the metal ions when present in milligram quantities. It is also possible to separate cobalt selectively in presence of other metal ions as cadmium, zinc, iron, nickel, etc.

WITH the introduction of combined ion exchange solvent extraction technique (CIESE), relatively great attention has been paid to the cation exchange studies and separation of various elements¹. In most of the cases, acetone-hydrochloric acid mixture or tetrahydrofuran-hydrochloric acid mixture has been used as eluent. An effective separation of large amounts of iron(III) from cobalt, nickel and aluminium is possible using tetrahydrofuran-hydrochloric acid mixtures as eluents². Korkisch et al have reported the selective separation of cobalt³ and uranium⁴ on a cation exchanger Dowex 50, X8. Acetone-hydrochloric acid mixtures have been used to separate calcium from copper, zinc, mercury(II), cadmium and iron⁵, copper from nickel⁶. Distribution coefficients for 53 elements in 1.2 M HCl-water-acetone medium on Dowex 50, X12 resin have been reported by Peters and Del Fiore⁷. Strelow has reported separation of aluminium, gallium, indium and thallium by the CIESE technique⁸. Studies of nickel sorption from aqueous organic solutions of inorganic acids have been reported by Lastit, Alimarin and Belyavskaya⁹.

Experimental

Reagents and Solutions

Stock solutions of metal ions used in the work were prepared by dissolving their AR grade salts in 3 N hydrochloric acid. In all the cases, the solutions prepared contained about 5 mg of metal ion/ml.

Solvent used was of reagent grade.

The acid cation exchanger, Amberlite IR-120 was used in the experiments. The column prepared had a height of about 22 cm and diameter 1.2 cm.

A stock EDTA solution (0.05 M) was prepared and standardized. For the determination of metal ions in eluate and in batch experiments (determination of distribution coefficients), EDTA titrations were performed following standard procedures.

Results

Determination of Distribution coefficients :

The distribution coefficients were determined by the batch equilibrium method¹⁰. Each equilibrium experiment was performed in 50 ml of mixture consisting of 0 or 40 to 90% acetone and 10 ml of 6 N hydrochloric acid and water up to 100%, and containing 5 mg of metal ion. The overall acidity of all the mixtures was 0.6 N hydrochloric acid. To the mixture, nearly 1 gm of dry resin was added and an equilibrium was set up by agitating the mixture on a shaking machine for eight hours. Resin was separated by filtration and filtrate was analysed quantitatively for the metal ion. The values of distribution coefficients for iron(III), cobalt(II) and nickel(II) are recorded in Table 1.

TABLE 1—DISTRIBUTION COEFFICIENTS OF IRON, COBALT AND NICKEL IN ACETONE-HCl MIXTURES

	Solvent mixture	Distribution coefficients		
		Fe(III)	Co(II)	Ni(II)
(1)	90% acetone+10% 6 M HCl	7	9	186
(2)	80% acetone+20% 3 M HCl	16	110	184
(3)	70% acetone+30% 2 M HCl	158	112	99
(4)	60% acetone+40% 1.5 M HCl	273	105	75
(5)	50% acetone+50% 1.2 M HCl	156	101	211
(6)	40% acetone+60% 1 M HCl	150	175	161
(7)	0.6 M HCl	117	98	30

An experimental error of the measurement of distribution coefficient was observed. It was about 10%. The values obtained above in different solvent systems can be interpreted in terms of the separation factor (K_a). Higher the deviation of separation factor from one, higher is the selectivity and simpler are the conditions of separation. From Table 1 it is clear that Fe(III) has distribution coefficient of 16 in 80% acetone-HCl mixture as compared to 110 for Co(II) and 184 for Ni(II). This means on elution with 80% acetone-HCl mixture, the least strongly adsorbed ion on the

resin will be Fe(III) while Co(II) and Ni(II) will be retained on the resin. Fe(III) will be washed out first but Co(II) and Ni(II) will remain adsorbed. Once Fe(III) is removed, Co(II) and Ni(II) can then be separated by eluting with 90% acetone-HCl mixture. The values of distribution coefficients in this solvent mixture have large difference. On washing the column with this mixture, will selectively elute least adsorbed Co(II) while Ni(II) will be retained. Finally Ni(II) can be washed out with 0.6 M HCl. It is also concluded from the values of distribution coefficients that only these three solvent systems can be satisfactorily used for separation purpose.

Separation of iron, cobalt and nickel

The resin column was prepared and it was first washed with 80% acetone-HCl mixture. The volume used was 100 ml. Twenty ml of mixture of Fe(III), Co(II) and Ni(II) in 3N HCl was taken and to it 80 ml of acetone were added. This solution (which is now 80% in acetone and 20% in 3NHCl) was passed through the column at a flow rate of 1 ml/minute. 200 ml more of the solution (80% acetone-HCl) were passed through the column at the same flow rate. This quantitatively eluted out iron. Cobalt was next separated with 90% acetone-HCl mixture, 150 ml of this eluent were required for complete elution of cobalt. The cobalt eluate was deep blue in colour. Finally nickel was separated by washing with hydrochloric acid. The concentrations of iron, cobalt and nickel in the solutions were determined volumetrically by EDTA titrations.

Table 2 below shows the results obtained in typical separations.

	Metal ion taken (mg)	Found (mg)	Per cent. recovery
(1)	Fe—13.16	13.16	100
	Co— 7.36	7.65	103.9
	Ni—10.57	10.25	96.9
(2)	Fe—22.35	22.12	98.9
	Co—10.90	11.12	102.1
	Ni—15.86	15.54	97.9

Presence of other elements

The presence of the following elements in the separation process was studied, Cu(II), Zn(II), Mg(II), Cd(II) and Al(III). The distribution coefficients of these metals in 80%, 90% acetone-HCl mixtures and in HCl alone were determined. The values obtained are recorded below in Table 3.

Solvent mixture	Distribution coefficients				
	Cu(II)	Zn(II)	Mg(II)	Cd(II)	Al(III)
80% acetone-HCl	3	1	164	1	230
90% acetone-HCl	1	1	86	5	230
0.6 M HCl	2	33	30	17	185

Mixture containing 10 mg each, of these metal ions and Fe, Co and Ni was prepared. Separation was followed using 80% acetone-HCl and 90% acetone-HCl and HCl solutions. The first eluate contained the following metal ions Fe, Cu, Zn, Cd. Second eluate contained Co only while in nickel fraction, Mg and Al got eluated. The values of distribution coefficients also support the observations.

From the results obtained in the studies, it is seen that the selectivity of separation of cobalt from other elements in acetone-HCl medium is far greater than in pure hydrochloric acid solution. Separation of cobalt from Cu(II), Zn(II), Mg(II) and Cd(II) using HCl alone as eluent is not possible because of similarity of distribution coefficients. For trivalent ions as Fe(III), Al(III) large quantities of resin are required for separation. These limitations can be overcome in acetone-HCl systems and cobalt can be selectively separated from the elements listed in Table 3.

A quantitative separation of cobalt from these elements was achieved. Table 4 below shows the results obtained.

Other ion present, mg	Amount of Co recovered, mg	Per cent. recovery
Ni(II) 10	6.93	100
Mg(II) 10	6.69	96.53
{Ni(II) 15 {Mg(II) 15	6.628	96
Cu(II) 10	6.93	100
Zn(II) 10	6.93	100
{Mg(II) 10 {Cu(II) 10 {Zn(II)} 10	6.80	98.12

The experiments were done using 5 to 50 mg of cobalt and varying amounts of other metal ions. After selective separation of cobalt, quantitative recovery of the elements is also possible.

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